

Studies on Hydroxamic Acids. Part VI : Gravimetric Determination and Separation of Beryllium, Yttrium, Dysprosium and Erbium with *N-m-Tolyl-m-Nitrobenzohydroxamic Acid*

Y. K. AGRAWAL*

Department of Chemistry, Govt. Science College, Rewa (M. P.)

Manuscript received 3 June 1976, revised 17 March 1977, accepted 24 November 1977

A quantitative determination and separation of Be^{2+} , Y^{3+} , Tb^{3+} , Dy^{3+} and Er^{3+} in presence of various diverse ions was made by precipitation with *N-m-tolyl-m-nitrobenzohydroxamic acid*. The complexes having the composition $(\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_2\text{O}_4)_n\text{M}$ were weighed directly after drying at 110° .

THE analytical potentialities and physico-chemical properties of *N-m-tolyl-m-nitrobenzohydroxamic acid* (*N-m-T-m-NBHA*)¹⁻³ reveals that it is a good complexing reagent. In continuation with our previous work⁴⁻¹⁰ the further use of this reagent for separation and gravimetric determination of Be, Tb, Dy and Er is described.

Experimental

Chemicals :

All the chemicals used were of highest purity available.

Reagents :

A reagent *N-m-tolyl-m-nitrobenzohydroxamic acid* has been synthesised is described elsewhere¹¹ and 0.1% alcoholic solution was used for precipitation of metal ions.

The 0.001 *M* solution of metal ions were prepared and final concentration were determined volumetrically¹².

A 1% solution of masking agent (cyanide, oxalate, or Mg-EDTA) was prepared by dissolving the requisite amount in double distilled water.

Procedure :

In a litre beaker, 10 ml solution of metal ions (Be, Y, Tb, Dy, or Er) and about 500 ml distilled water were heated at 60° on water bath. The pH of precipitation was adjusted with ammonium acetate and acetic acid (Table 1). Then about 20 ml alcoholic solution of reagent (*N-m-T-m-NBHA*) was added dropwise with constant stirring followed by

0.01 solution of ammonium hydroxide until complete precipitation was obtained. The granular complexes thus obtained were digested for 20 min on water bath, filtered through fine porosity filter paper washed with first alcohol water mixture and then water and mounted on a steel planchette. The complexes were dried and weighed as $(\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_2\text{O}_4)_n\text{M}$, (where M = Be, Y, Tb, Dy, or Er).

Results and Discussion

The pH of precipitations and the data on gravimetric determination for Be^{2+} , Y^{3+} , Tb^{3+} , Dy^{3+} , and Er^{3+} with *N-m-tolyl-m-nitrobenzohydroxamic acid* are given in Table 1. The data for separation are given in Tables 2-3.

TABLE-1 GRAVIMETRIC DETERMINATION OF Be^{2+} , Y^{3+} , Tb^{3+} , Dy^{3+} AND Er^{3+} WITH *N-m-TOLYL-m-NITROBENZOHYDROXAMIC ACID*

Compd. No.	Metal	pH of pptn		wt. in mg.			
I	Be^{2+}	5.5-6.2	taken	0.09	0.18	0.36	1.80
			wt. of ppt	5.50	11.01	22.64	109.56
			found	0.09	0.18	0.37	1.79
II	Y^{3+}	5.5-6.5	taken	0.89	1.78	3.57	8.93
			wt. of ppt	9.05	18.08	36.30	90.40
			found	0.89	1.77	3.57	8.92
III	Tb^{3+}	9.0-9.5	taken	1.59	3.18	6.36	15.90
			wt. of ppt	9.73	19.50	38.88	97.35
			found	1.59	3.19	6.36	15.91
IV	Dy^{3+}	9.2-9.6	taken	1.62	2.43	8.10	16.20
			wt. of ppt	9.70	14.55	48.65	97.25
			found	1.61	2.42	8.10	16.19
V	Er^{3+}	9.5-10.0	taken	1.67	2.50	3.34	8.35
			wt. of ppt	9.80	14.65	19.60	48.95
			found	1.67	2.49	3.39	8.34

* Present address : Dr. Y. K. Agrawal, Reader in Analytical Chemistry, Pharmacy-Department, Faculty of Technology & Engineering, M. S. University of Baroda, Kalabhavan, Baroda-390001, (Gujarat).

TABLE—2 SEPARATION OF Be(II) FROM DIVERSE IONS

Be(II) taken mg	Diverse ions taken (mg)	Ma-king agents	Be(II) found mg
0.36	Ag ⁺ (50)	Cyanide	0.36
0.36	Mn ²⁺ (75)	Cyanide	0.36
0.36	Zn ²⁺ (75)	Cyanide	0.36
0.36	Cd ²⁺ (75)	Cyanide	0.37
0.36	Hg ²⁺ (100)	Cyanide	0.37
1.86	Cu ²⁺ (100)	Cyanide	1.88
1.86	Mg ²⁺ (75)	Cyanide	1.84
1.86	Fe ²⁺ (80)	Cyanide	1.85
1.86	Ga ³⁺ (80)	Cyanide	1.86
1.86	Al ³⁺ (80)	Mg-EDTA	1.87
1.86	V ⁵⁺ (80)	Mg-EDTA	1.84
1.86	Mo ⁶⁺ (100)	Mg-EDTA	1.85
1.86	Bb ²⁺ (80)	NTA	1.85
1.86	Pd ²⁺ (80)	NTA	1.86
0.36	Sn ²⁺ (100)	NTA	0.36
0.36	Bi ³⁺ (100)	NTA	0.36
0.36	Zr ⁴⁺ (100)	NTA	0.37
1.86	Ti ⁴⁺ (100)	NTA	1.86
1.86	La ³⁺ (80)	NTA	1.86
1.86	Ce ³⁺ (80)	NTA	1.86
1.86	Pr ³⁺ (80)	NTA	1.85
1.86	Nd ³⁺ (80)	NTA	1.85
1.86	Sb ³⁺ (80)	IODATE	1.85
1.86	Th ⁴⁺ (80)	a	1.86
0.36	U ⁶⁺ (80)	a	0.37

a by adjusting pH; NTA nitrilotriacetate

TABLE—3 SEPARATION OF Y(III), Tb(III), Dy(III) AND Er(III) FROM DIVERSE IONS

Metal ion taken : Y³⁺ 1.78 mg ; Tb³⁺ 3.18 mg ;
Dy³⁺ 2.43 mg ; Er³⁺ 2.50 mg.

Diverse ions taken mg	Masking Agents	Metal ions found, mg			
		Y ³⁺	Tb ³⁺	Dy ³⁺	Er ³⁺
Ag ⁺ (50)	Cyanide	1.77	3.18	2.44	2.50
Mn ²⁺ (75)	Cyanide	1.78	3.18	2.44	2.50
Zn ²⁺ (75)	Cyanide	1.77	3.18	2.45	2.50
Cd ²⁺ (75)	Cyanide	1.79	3.20	2.43	2.52
Hg ²⁺ (100)	Cyanide	1.78	3.17	2.43	2.53
Cu ²⁺ (100)	Cyanide	1.78	3.16	2.43	2.50
Mg ²⁺ (75)	Cyanide	1.77	3.20	2.43	2.48
Fe ²⁺ (80)	Cyanide	1.76	3.20	2.43	2.51
Ga ³⁺ (80)	Cyanide	1.78	3.17	2.43	2.50
Pb ²⁺ (80)	Citrate + oxalate	1.78	3.17	2.43	2.50
Sb ³⁺ (80)	Citrate + oxalate	1.78	3.17	2.42	2.48
Pd ²⁺ (80)	Citrate + oxalate	1.78	3.17	2.42	2.51
Sn ²⁺ (100)	Citrate + oxalate	1.77	3.17	2.42	2.50
Bi ³⁺ 9(100)	Citrate + oxalate	1.76	3.18	2.44	2.51
Zr ⁴⁺ (100)	Citrate + oxalate	1.76	3.18	2.42	2.51
Ti ⁴⁺ (80)	Citrate + oxalate	1.78	3.19	2.43	2.50
Al ³⁺ (80)	Mg-EDTA	1.78	3.19	2.44	2.50
V ⁵⁺ (80)	Mg-EDTA	1.78	3.19	2.43	2.50
W ⁶⁺ (100)	Mg-EDTA	1.77	3.19	2.43	2.50
U ⁶⁺ (80)	a	1.79	3.18	2.43	2.49
Th ⁴⁺ (80)	a	1.79	3.18	2.43	2.49
La ³⁺ (80)	a	1.79	3.18	2.44	2.49
Ce ³⁺ (80)	a	1.78	3.18	2.42	2.50
Sm ³⁺ (80)	a	1.78	3.18	5.42	2.50
Be ²⁺ (80)	a	1.78	3.18	2.44	2.50

a by adjusting the pH

1. Separation of Be, Y, Tb, Dy, or Er from Common Metal Ions :

(i) *Using Masking Agents* : Into 10 ml of 0.001 M solution of Be, Tb, Dy, or Er with the desired foreign metal ions were and diluted to about 500 ml. Then 10 ml of 1% KCN solution was added and pH was adjusted. The contents were heated to 60°. The reagent solution was added dropwise with constant stirring. The complex thus formed was allowed to stand for about 20 min on water bath. It was filtered, washed, dried and weighed as before. The metals could be separated from and determined in the presence of Ag⁺, Mn²⁺, Zn²⁺, Cd²⁺, Hg²⁺, Cu²⁺, Mg²⁺, Fe²⁺ and Ga³⁺.

Y, Tb, Dy, and Er could be separated from and determined in presence of Pb²⁺, Pd²⁺, Sb³⁺, Sn²⁺, Bi³⁺, Zr⁴⁺ and Ti⁴⁺, with 10 ml of 1% citrate and oxalate instead of cyanide solution. Be, Y, Tb, Dy and Er could be separated from Al³⁺, V⁵⁺ and Mo⁶⁺ by using Mg-EDTA as a masking agent.

Be could be separated from Pb²⁺, Pd²⁺, Sn²⁺, Bi³⁺, Zr⁴⁺ and Ti⁴⁺ and La³⁺, Ce³⁺, Pr³⁺, Nd³⁺, using nitrilotriacetate as masking agent. Be could also be separated from Sb³⁺ by masking with iodate.

(ii) *By adjusting pH* : 10 ml solution (0.001) of metal ion (Y, Tb, Dy or Er) was diluted to 500 ml and mixed with diverse ions. The Ag⁺, Cu²⁺, Pb²⁺, Zn²⁺, Cd²⁺, Al³⁺, Th⁴⁺ and U⁶⁺ were precipitated below pH 5.5 using excess of reagent (N-m-T-m-NBHA). The precipitate was filtered, washed thoroughly and from mother liquor Y, Tb, Dy or Er was precipitated by adjusting the pH.

2. Characteristic of the Complexes :

The complexes are white in colour. They are freely soluble in dioxane, chloroform, toluene and fairly soluble in ethanol. These complexes were decomposed when treated with concentrated nitric, perchloric and sulphuric acids. The IR spectra and analytical results indicate that the composition of the complexes are (C₁₄H₁₁N₂O₄)_nM (Table 4).

Acknowledgement

The author indebted to Professor A. S. Kapur, Head, Chemistry Department, Govt. College, Rewa and Professor A. B Biswas and Professor S. C. Bhattacharyya, I. I. T, Powai for providing the necessary facilities and discussion.

TABLE-4

Copt. No.	Molecular weight		IR spectra cm^{-1}		Analysis %					
	Found	Calculated	$\nu\text{C}=\text{O}$	$\nu\text{N}=\text{O}$	C	found N	M	C	calculated N	M
I	822.80	822.78	1565	913	61.34	10.22	1.09	61.31	10.25	1.10
II	902.60	902.68	1560	913	55.90	9.30	9.87	55.88	9.31	9.85
III	972.70	972.69	1550	915	51.85	8.62	16.34	51.86	8.64	16.34
IV	976.20	976.27	1555	915	51.65	8.62	16.65	51.67	8.61	16.64
V	981.00	981.03	1560	915	51.40	8.55	17.05	51.42	8.56	17.05

References

1. Y. K. AGRAWAL and H. L. KAPOOR, *Roes, Chemi.*, 1975, **49**, 1431.
2. Y. K. AGRAWAL and H. L. KAPOOR, *Ann. di Chim.*, communicated.
3. Y. K. AGRAWAL, *Indian J. Chem.*, communicated.
4. H. L. KAPOOR and Y. K. AGRAWAL, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1975, **13**, 957.
5. Y. K. AGRAWAL and H. L. KAPOOR, *Analysis*, 1975, **3**, 424.
6. P. C. VERMA, Y. K. AGRAWAL and P. V. KHADIKAR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, **52**, 176.
7. H. L. KAPOOR, Y. K. AGRAWAL and P. C. VERMA, *Talanta*, 1975, **22**, 193.
8. Y. K. AGRAWAL, *Sci & Cult.*, communicated.
9. Y. K. AGRAWAL and H. L. KAPOOR, *Talanta*, 1976, **23**, 235.
10. Y. K. AGRAWAL and H. L. KAPOOR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, **53**, 174.
11. Y. K. AGRAWAL and S. G. TANDON, *J. Chem. Engg. Data*, 1971, **16**, 371.
12. F. J. WELCHER, "The Analytical Uses of Ethylenediamine Tetraacetic Acid", Van Nostrand, Princeton, 1961.